

Synthesis and biological potential of nitrones of 4-chlorobenzaldehyde and ethylvanillin

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Abstract : Nitrones of 4-chlorobenzaldehyde (1a-6a) and ethylvanillin (1b-6b) were synthesized by condensing 4-chlorobenzaldehyde (a) and ethylvanillin (b) with phenylhydroxylamines (1-6) in equimolar ratio. The synthesized nitrones were characterized on the basis of elemental analysis and spectral studies and screened for antifungal potential against six phytopathogenic fungi and nematicidal activity against two nematodes.

Keywords : Nitrones, 4-chlorobenzaldehyde, ethylvanillin, antifungal potential, nematicidal activity.

Introduction

Synthesis and assaying of biological activity of the compounds containing carbon-nitrogen double bond has received considerable interest in recent years^{1,2}. Nitrones contain in addition to carbon-nitrogen double bond, an oxygen atom attached to nitrogen by co-ordinate bond. The effect of nature of the substituent and its position on the biological activity of Schiff bases, compounds containing carbon-nitrogen double bond, has been fully investigated^{3,4}, whereas very little work has been carried out to study the biological activity of nitrones^{5,6}. The presence of chloro⁷ substituent in a compound or electron-releasing groups⁸ in the C-phenyl ring has been reported to increase the activity of the parent compound. In continuation of our work on study of nitrones⁹, this paper describes the synthesis of nitrones of 4-chlorobenzaldehyde and ethylvanillin, their characterization and evaluation for antifungal and nematicidal activity.

Results and discussion

Condensation of 4-chlorobenzaldehyde (a) and ethylvanillin (b) with phenylhydroxylamine and substituted phenylhydroxylamines (1-6) in equimolar ratio resulted in the formation of products 1a-6a and 1b-6b respectively which were identified and confirmed as C-(4-chlorophenyl)-N-phenylnitron (1a), C-(4-chlorophenyl)-N-(4-chlorophenyl)nitron (2a), C-(4-chlorophenyl)-N-(3-chlorophenyl)nitron (3a), C-(4-chlorophenyl)-N-(2-chlorophenyl)nitron (4a), C-(4-chlorophenyl)-N-(4-tolyl)nitron (5a), C-(4-chlorophenyl)-N-(3-tolyl)nitron

(6a), C-(3-ethoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl)-N-phenylnitron (1b), C-(3-ethoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl)-N-(4-chlorophenyl)nitron (2b), C-(3-ethoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl)-N-(3-chlorophenyl)nitron (3b), C-(3-ethoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl)-N-(2-chlorophenyl)nitron (4b), C-(3-ethoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl)-N-(4-tolyl)nitron (5b) and C-(3-ethoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl)-N-(3-tolyl)nitron (6b) respectively (Table 1) on the basis of elemental analysis and spectral studies.

The infrared spectra of the compounds contained bands at 1610-1600 and 1300-1260 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of carbon-nitrogen double bond and N→O linkage respectively. In PMR spectra, all the protons resonated at the expected field (Table 2). The mass spectrum of 2a gave molecular ion peak at m/z 266 and the base peak at m/z 111 due to C₁₀H₄ species.

The nitrones 1a-6a and 1b-6b were evaluated *in vitro* for antifungal potential against *Alternaria alternata*, *Curvularia lunata*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Helminthosporium tetramera*, *Myrothecium roridum* and *Ustilago tritici* by spore germination inhibition method¹⁰. The results have been expressed in terms of ED₅₀ value i.e. the effective dose at which 50 per cent spore germination inhibition occurred (Table 3). All the test nitrones except 2a and 4a showed ED₅₀ value less than 1000 ppm against *A. alternata*. Four compounds (3a, 6a, 5b, 6b) possessed promising potential against the fungus and the best among these was C-(4-chlorophenyl)-N-(3-tolyl)nitron (6a) with ED₅₀ value of 80 ppm. The nitrones of 4-chlorobenzaldehyde (1a-6a) possessed poor to moderate activity against *C. lunata*. However, the nitrones of ethylvanillin except 1b

Table 1. Characteristics of nitrones

Compd.	R	R'	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Molecular formula
1a	4-Cl	H	150	65	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ NOCl
2a	4-Cl	4-Cl	115	45	C ₁₃ H ₉ NOCl ₂
3a	4-Cl	3-Cl	86	81	C ₁₃ H ₉ NOCl ₂
4a	4-Cl	2-Cl	Oil	60	C ₁₃ H ₉ NOCl ₂
5a	4-Cl	4-CH ₃	45	84	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ NOCl
6a	4-Cl	3-CH ₃	40	80	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ NOCl
1b	3-OC ₂ H ₅ 4-OH	H	160	62	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ NO ₃
2b	3-OC ₂ H ₅ 4-OH	4-Cl	110	51	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ NO ₃ Cl
3b	3-OC ₂ H ₅ 4-OH	3-Cl	100	57	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ NO ₃ Cl
4b	3-OC ₂ H ₅ 4-OH	2-Cl	118	53	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ NO ₃ Cl
5b	3-OC ₂ H ₅ 4-OH	4-CH ₃	140	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ NO ₃
6b	3-OC ₂ H ₅ 4-OH	3-CH ₃	132	60	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ NO ₃

Table 2. PMR spectra of nitrones

Compd.	Signals (δ) due to protons of			
	Ar-H	CH	CH ₃	O-CH ₂ -CH ₃
1a	7.0-8.0 (9H, m)	8.3 (s)	-	-
2a	6.9-8.1 (8H, m)	8.4 (s)	-	-
3a	6.9-8.1 (8H, m)	8.4 (s)	-	-
4a	6.9-8.2 (8H, m)	8.5 (s)	-	-
5a	7.1-8.2 (8H, m)	8.7 (s)	2.5 (s)	-
6a	7.0-8.1 (8H, m)	8.6 (s)	2.4 (s)	-
1b	6.9-7.8 (8H, m)	8.2 (s)	-	-
2b	7.0-8.0 (7H, m)	8.3 (s)	-	4.3 (q), 1.5 (t)
3b	6.9-8.0 (7H, m)	8.3 (s)	-	4.2 (q), 1.4 (t)
4b	7.0-8.1 (7H, m)	8.4 (s)	-	4.2 (q), 1.4 (t)
5b	7.1-8.1 (7H, m)	8.5 (s)	2.5 (s)	4.1 (q), 1.4 (t)
6b	7.2-8.2 (7H, m)	8.4 (s)	2.5 (s)	4.2 (q), 1.5 (t)

Table 3. Antifungal potential of nitrones

Compd.	ED ₅₀ values (ppm) against					
	<i>A. alternata</i>	<i>C. lunata</i>	<i>F. oxysporum</i>	<i>H. tetramera</i>	<i>M. roridum</i>	<i>U. tritici</i>
1a	690	730	650	*	185	750
2a	*	*	*	*	60	*
3a	200	860	560	*	160	*
4a	*	430	*	*	150	600
5a	330	340	300	*	190	740
6a	80	290	570	350	350	540
1b	640	590	*	*	350	*
2b	360	180	800	180	260	780
3b	360	160	740	180	240	890
4b	350	170	720	190	250	750
5b	180	180	750	170	230	820
6b	190	190	730	180	260	610

*More than 1000 ppm.

showed promising potential against this fungus with ED₅₀ values between 160–190 ppm. Nine test compounds have been found to possess moderate activity against *F. oxysporum*. Only one nitrone of 4-chlorobenzaldehyde (6a) had ED₅₀ value less than 1000 ppm against *H. tetramera*. Five nitrones of ethylvanillin (2b–6b) possessed promising potential against this fungus with ED₅₀ values less than 200 ppm. All the test nitrones have been found to be quite effective against *M. roridum* and the most potent compound was *C*-(4-chlorophenyl)-*N*-(4-chlorophenyl)nitrone (2a) with ED₅₀ value of 60 ppm. Nine nitrones possessed moderate protency against *U. tritici*.

A comparison of antifungal potential of nitrones of ethylvanillin with those of vanillin has revealed that the ethoxy group has more pronounced effect on the antifungal activity. Thus the nitrones of ethylvanillin which contain ethoxy group in the *C*-phenyl ring possess better antifungal potential as compared to the nitrones of vanillin which have methoxy group in the *C*-phenyl ring. Introduction of chloro and methyl substituent in *N*-phenyl ring of nitrones of ethylvanillin results in enhancement of activity against three test fungi viz. *A. alternata*, *C. lunata* and *H. tetramera* whereas there is not much change in activity against the other three test fungi. However no such generalization can be drawn in case of nitrones of 4-chlorobenzaldehyde.

The synthesized compounds 1a–6a and 1b–6b were

screened for nematicidal activity against *Ditylenchus myceliophagus* and *Caenorhabditis elegans* using the aqueous *in vitro* screening technique¹¹. The results have been expressed in terms of percent mortality of nematodes at various concentrations. Four nitrones of 4-chlorobenzaldehyde (1a, 2a, 3a, 6a) have been found to cause more than 65% mortality against *D. myceliophagus* at 1000 ppm after 96 h exposure. Three compounds (1a, 2a, 6a) showed more than 50% mortality at 500 ppm but none of these compounds has inflicted more than 50% mortality at 250 ppm, the best results being shown by compounds 2a with 48% mortality. Same trend has been observed against *C. elegans*. Again four nitrones of 4-chlorobenzaldehyde (1a, 2a, 3a, 4a) have shown more than 74% mortality against *C. elegans* at 1000 ppm after 96 h exposure. The compounds 1a and 2a have induced more than 70% mortality at 500 ppm. At 250 ppm concentration the compound 1a has been found to possess 63% mortality. The parent compound (1a) has shown the best results against both the test nematodes. Introduction of a substituent in *N*-phenyl ring of nitrones of 4-chlorobenzaldehyde results in decline in the nematicidal potential and this decline is quite sharp if the substituent is electron-releasing methyl group. The nitrones of ethylvanillin (1b–6b) have been found to possess poor nematicidal activity against test nematodes and inflicted less than 50% mortality against both *D. myceliophagus* and *C. elegans* at 1000 ppm after 96 h exposure.

Fig. 1. The reaction sequence.

Experimental

All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis and the melting points are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded using Perkin-Elmer, Model RX-1 FTIR spectrophotometer using KBr discs. PMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AC 300 F NMR spectrophotometer using CDCl_3 as solvent. Mass spectra were recorded as a VG Analytical Mass spectrometer.

Synthesis of nitrones : 4-Chlorobenzaldehyde/ethylvanillin (0.1 mol) was dissolved in dry chloroform (250 ml) taken in a conical flask (500 ml). Then phenyl hydroxylamine/substituted phenylhydroxylamine (0.1 mol), prepared by the reduction of nitrobenzene/substituted nitrobenzene with zinc dust and ammonium chloride, was added to the above solution with stirring. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. The excess of solvent was then removed and the contents were cooled. The solid which separated out was filtered and crystallized from methanol to get respective nitrone.

In vitro screening of nitrones for antifungal activity : Each compound (20 mg) was dissolved in ethanol (0.5 ml) and sterilized distilled water (9.5 ml) was then added to prepare the stock solution of 2000 ppm. The stock solutions were serially diluted to obtain the required concentrations of the compounds. The suspension of the test

fungus was mixed separately with the solution of the compound in equal amount in the cavities of the cavity slides. These slides were kept in petriplates lined with moist filter paper and incubated for 20 h at 25 ± 1 °C. The slides were checked for percent germination occurred and percent spore germination inhibition was calculated and ED_{50} values were determined.

In vitro testing of the compounds for nematicidal activity : About 100 nematodes of each genera were exposed to 2 ml solution of the test compound and observations for the number of living or dead nematodes were recorded after an interval of 96 h. The immobile nematodes with a definite posture were recorded as dead. After 96 h the nematodes were transferred to distilled water and possible reversal of immobilized nematodes was recorded.

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